

GENERAL CONCEPTS OF WRITTEN SPEECH

Mitanova Shahlo Nematullayevna

Samarkand state foreign

languages institute PhD student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11560795>

Abstract : This in the article written speech of activity written in the form done to be increased productive type being , of this as a result we to the interlocutor effect to do through to our goal to reach about word goes Also, from the Linguistic point of view, it is shown that writing is considered a graphic system as one of the forms of expression.

Key words : language , style , method , reading , writing speech , literary style , oral speech , conversation , language , thoughts , speech activity .

Introduction.

From a methodological point of view, writing is understood as "students' acquisition of the graphic and orthographic system of a foreign language as an aid to recording speech and language material for better memorization, as well as oral speech and reading." Writing is the process of expressing ideas graphically.

Written speech is a type of speech activity related to the transmission of information in a graphic form in accordance with the communication situation. As Stanislav Jelinek writes, it is the written production of statements that occur in the process of communication and language learning.

Written speech includes two types of speech activity: productive (writing) and receptive (reading).

During communication, both in life and in the course of the lesson, with the help of speech and depending on the situation, we exchange information.

Main part.

Speech activity is "an active and purposeful process of receiving and transmitting information in various communication situations using speech means."

Speech writing is the ability to convey ideas in written form. Expressing thoughts in written form is called writing. The new dictionary of methodological terms and concepts (theory and practice of language teaching) gives the following definition: Speech skill is the ability of a person to perform one or another speech act in the context of solving communicative problems and on the basis of developed skills and acquired knowledge. is considered

From a pedagogical point of view, speech skills are the student's ability to participate in various types of speech activities based on acquired knowledge and developed skills.

It should be recognized that speech skill is a speech act that has reached the level of automaticity as a result of exercises (preparation, teaching - language, communication).

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, a skill is understood as an automated action using phonetic, lexical and grammatical material in the process of receptive

or productive speech activity. Accordingly, skills are distinguished: phonetic (auditory pronunciation), grammatical, lexical and motor (writing).

Speech and writing play an active role in human speech activity, as both types serve to transmit information.

IS Kryuchkova and NV Moshchinskaya in their book "Practical methods of teaching a foreign language" emphasized that written speech is a type of speech activity, like speech, which is aimed at "producing" speech and therefore effective.

In teaching foreign languages, written speech can be considered as a methodological tool for teaching other types of speech activity. As Kryuchkova and Moshinskaya wrote in their book "Practical methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language", written speech also develops other types of speech activity. With the help of writing, we learn the material better, we can repeat and reinforce it. Speaking can be mastered without writing skills, but with the help of writing, we can master speaking faster.

What is said can be written, what has been written can be re-told. One of the founders of modern linguistics, Ferdinand de Saussure, said of the relationship between written and spoken language: "The former exists to express the latter. It is impossible not to agree that oral and written speech are closely related to each other."

First of all, as the linguist NLShebko wrote, mastering written speech is the most difficult compared to other skills and competencies. To learn to write, you need to practice, you need to try, you need special training exercises. To learn to write, a person must know the graphic and spelling system, standard grammar, vocabulary, etc. A person naturally acquires oral speech. You can quickly learn to speak a foreign language in the same way that children learn to speak their mother tongue in the appropriate language environment, i.e. in a natural setting. That is, unlike speaking, one must learn to write, while learning to speak comes naturally.

In the absence of direct communication, the writer expands the statement to avoid misunderstanding of his ideas. In this regard, writing contains additional information, definitions and specific features, so writing is distinguished by the breadth and completeness of expression, as well as logical completeness. In oral speech, it is easier, additional information and explanations are required using emotional volitional aspects (intonation, pauses, facial expressions, gestures, visual communication). Written speech does not have a number of such advantages. Graphical means (punctuation) in written speech cannot express everything that is said by non-verbal means in oral speech.

In written speech, it is impossible to know the interlocutor's attitude and react instantly. Unlike oral speech, written speech has no connection with the communication partner and cannot respond to the listener's reaction, it can only assume the absence of the receiver and intermediate feedback; In oral speech, depending on the reaction of the interlocutor, the next sentence may change. That's why writing is constant and speaking is variable.

The writer should organize his speech more carefully. The written text should be more clearly structured, because it has the possibility of verification. Written speech cannot be spontaneous, it must have a structure and be logically organized. One of the main characteristics of spoken text is its spontaneity. The speaker can stop and improvise, sometimes losing the logic of the sentence.

It takes more time to create a written statement. We strive to present information consistently and logically, clearly and concisely, because there will be no opportunity to change, repeat or explain what is written. Therefore, it is a well-thought-out, polished, written language in which the author restores something, redevelops it, tries to format what is written correctly. However, information can be obtained more quickly from a written message than from a verbal message. The speed of information transfer - writing letters is much slower than speaking.

Written speech is characterized by the field of official communication (written message, presentation, description, statement, announcement, description, business correspondence is personal correspondence closely related to spoken and spoken language);

Perception of writing is visual and speech is auditory, written speech is inherently monophonic, and spoken speech is dialogic. However, with the development of technology, it is now possible to use written speech, as well as oral speech, in dialogue (Internet chat, SMS by phone, correspondence on Skype, social networks, etc.).

Regarding the storage of information, spoken speech is remembered only with the help of our memory (with the exception of voice recorders, video recordings, etc.) stored on paper or in electronic form.

It is known that there are different approaches to teaching writing in modern methods of teaching foreign languages.

Activity-based - based on the individual creativity of students or a learning group, the formation of awareness and ideas occurs during the process. The purpose of the process is to produce text. The activity approach is based on the principles of personal-activity learning. The main feature of this approach is to focus on the process rather than the result of the activity, the independence of the student in choosing the content and linguistic form of his creative written works (compositions, essays, tales, poems, etc.). Paying attention to something personal increases the motivation to learn a foreign language.

Conclusion.

The activity approach includes combined methods: communicative and intensive methods, including activation methods.

In the activity approach, the teacher's role is to encourage students to work creatively. Thus, we can call the activity approach the most suitable for creative writing. Creative writing allows students to use existing lexical and grammatical skills, express their individuality, become aware of cross-cultural differences, and use their writing to practice reading and speaking skills.

References:

1. Akishina AA, OE Kogon . Let 's teach let's learn . Foreign language as Russian language teachers for . - 7th edition. M.: Russian language Courses , 2010. – 256 p.14.
2. Zhitkova EV O and written speech between similarity and differences (rus in) // Language and culture - 2009. - No. 3. - With 102.
3. Kapitonova TI, LVMoskovkin . Russian language foreign language as teaching methodology and technologies . - 2nd edition, stereotype . - M.: Russian language Courses , 2009. - 312 p.3.
4. Kryuchkova LS, Moshinskaya NV Rus language foreign language as of teaching practical methods . M: 2009. – p. 186.

5. Purm R., Jelinek S., Vesely J.. Russian of the language didactics , selected chapters . Gaudeamus , 2003 p. 180.
6. Shibko NL Rus language foreign language as teaching methodology . Non-philological specializations according to foreign students for educational and methodological complex . BDU. Minsk 2011. - p. 78.
7. Voronina AZ Foreign languages teaching acceleration issue about . Entrepreneurship and professional communication for foreign of the language linguistics and language didactics issues , Russia Federation government in the presence of Finance Academy . Moscow 2006. - p. 18.
8. Khodera R. Chet languages didactics . - 2nd edition, Academy . Prague 2013. - p. 91.